

Organophosphonic Acids as Complexones. Part-VII. Divalent Metal Derivatives of 1-Aminoethylidenediphosphonic Acid and 1-Aminobenzylidenediphosphonic Acid

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Reactions of 1-aminoalkylidene-/arylidenediphosphonic acids with bivalent metal salts, Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} yielded solid products of general formula $M_2L \cdot xH_2O$, in which metal is hexa-coordinated as has been inferred from their electronic spectra. Coordination sites have been established from infrared studies. Subnormal magnetic moment values and other physical properties suggest them to be polymeric in nature.

COMPLEX forming properties of 1-hydroxyethylidenediphosphonic acid (HEDP) have been reported earlier from these laboratories^{1,2}. 1-Aminoalkylidenediphosphonic acids are structurally similar ligands. The basic centre -OH in 1-hydroxyalkylidenediphosphonic acids has been replaced by -NH₂ group in this type of ligands. These ligands have been reported to have herbicidal and fungicidal properties³. Therefore, with the view that metal ions might enhance these properties, in the present work attempt has been made to explore complexing potentialities of these ligands by isolating their metal derivatives from aqueous medium.

Experimental

1-Aminoethylidenediphosphonic acid (AEDP) was prepared by the reaction of acetanilide with phosphorus trichloride and diethylphosphite in 1 : 3 : 1 molar ratio⁴. 1-Aminobenzylidenediphosphonic acid (ABDP) has, however, been prepared by the reported method⁵.

Preparation of metal derivatives : Bivalent metal salts (B.D.H.) were used as such.

The metal derivatives of both AEDP and ABDP were prepared by mixing 0.002 mole of aqueous solution of metal salt with 0.001 mole of the ligand solution with constant stirring. In case of AEDP, it was followed by the dropwise addition of a solution 0.004 mole of NaOH. However, with ABDP, complex precipitation was possible even on direct mixing and there was no need for neutralisation of the liberated hydrogen ions. Addition of acetone/methanol to the reaction mixture helped in improving the yield of the product. The precipitates were washed with 50% acetone to free the product from starting metal salt and then dried at 60-70°. The analytical data showed the complexes as having general formula $M_2L \cdot xH_2O$, where L=AEDP or ABDP, and x=1-3.

Reactions in the 1 : 1 molar ratio of metal and ligand also resulted in the formation of M_2L complexes and no complexes with partial replacement of acidic hydrogens could be isolated.

Infrared spectra in the form of KBr pellets were recorded on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Mull spectra in the 200-2000 nm region were run on DMR-21 spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements at room temperature were made on PAR 155 vibrating sample magnetometer. Thermal analyses of some of the compounds were done at N.C.L., Pune in the atmosphere of air and in platinum crucible, using alumina as the standard.

Results and Discussion

Reaction between bivalent metal salt and 1-aminoethylidenediphosphonic acid (AEDP) or 1-aminobenzylidenediphosphonic acid (ABDP) in the molar ratio of 2 : 1 yielded compounds with general formula $M_2L \cdot xH_2O$, where x may have the value from 1 to 3 which were inferred from elemental analyses (Table 1). The compounds once precipitated did not dissolve in water or any other common organic solvent. The metal derivatives did not melt even up to 270°. The reactions can be represented by the following equation.

The structures of the complexes were determined by infrared and electronic spectral, and magnetic measurement studies.

The infrared spectrum of 1-aminoethylidenediphosphonic acid suggested that the ligand exists

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF METAL DERIVATIVES OF AEDP AND ABDP

Complex	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.
		M	P	
$\text{Mn}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	White	31.02 (31.68)	17.15 (17.87)	4.12
$\text{Co}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Blue violet	30.59 (31.62)	16.25 (16.63)	3.48
$\text{Ni}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light green	30.58 (30.07)	15.25 (15.88)	2.31
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light blue	33.13 (34.90)	16.75 (17.08)	1.39
$\text{Zn}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	White	32.89 (33.90)	15.86 (16.07)	—
$\text{Cd}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	White	49.01 (48.68)	13.21 (13.48)	—
$\text{Pb}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	White	63.02 (65.43)	9.65 (9.79)	—
$\text{Mn}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	White	29.65 (30.16)	15.41 (15.86)	4.04
$\text{Co}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Violet	28.71 (28.28)	15.12 (14.87)	3.85
$\text{Ni}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light green	28.64 (28.19)	15.35 (14.89)	2.5
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light blue	31.52 (31.14)	15.49 (15.19)	1.82
$\text{Zn}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	White	32.28 (31.76)	15.82 (15.06)	—
$\text{Cd}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	White	44.96 (44.43)	12.48 (12.26)	—
$\text{Pb}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_8\text{NP}_2) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	White	60.63 (59.60)	9.25 (8.97)	—

as a zwitterion. The two bands at 1160 and 1020 cm^{-1} correspond to $\nu_{\text{as}}\text{PO}_2$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}\text{PO}_2$ vibrations in HPO_3 group. In addition, $\nu_{\text{as}}\text{P}-\text{OH}$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}\text{P}-\text{OH}$ bands corresponding to $\text{P}(\text{OH})_2$ also appeared at 1000 and 940 cm^{-1} . Bands at 3160-2960 and 1500 cm^{-1} have been assigned to stretching and bending mode of NH_3^+ . Phosphoryl frequency was observed at 1200 cm^{-1} .

Infrared spectrum of 1-aminobenzylidenediphosphonic acid showed only two bands at 1010 and 930 cm^{-1} in the region of phosphonic group which could be assigned to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of $\text{P}(\text{OH})_2$ group. Phosphoryl stretching frequency, $\nu_{\text{P}=\text{O}}$, appeared at 1230 cm^{-1} . The stretching and bending mode of NH_3^+ group have been observed at 3400 cm^{-1} and 1580 cm^{-1} , respectively.

The frequencies of the principal bands in the IR spectra of AEDP and its metal derivatives have been given in Table 2. Stretching vibrations of phosphoryl group in case of metal derivatives have been observed at 1110-1155 cm^{-1} . The displacement of the band by 50-100 cm^{-1} towards lower frequency has been attributed to the formation of coordination

bond between phosphoryl oxygen and metal ion. Such observations have also been made in case of polyaminopolyphosphonic acids reported from these laboratories^{6,7} and are also in agreement with the observations of Khramov *et al.*⁸ for compounds of 1-hydroxyethylidenediphosphonic acid. The asymmetric and symmetric mode of stretching vibration of PO_3 group appeared at 1070-1020 and 1000-900 cm^{-1} ranges, respectively and splitting of these bands was observed. Such splitting is expected in view of the partial covalent character of $\text{M}-\text{O}$ bond due to lowering of the symmetry of PO_3 group.

Similar to AEDP complexes, lowering in $\nu_{\text{P}=\text{O}}$ has also been observed in metal derivatives of ABDP (Table 3) and absorptions due to asymmetric and symmetric modes of PO_3 group appeared at 1040 \pm 10 and 980-990 cm^{-1} , respectively.

Participation of NH_3^+ group in coordination to metal ion could not be inferred from the IR spectra due to $\text{C}-\text{N}$ bands being very weak and masking of $\text{N}-\text{H}$ bands by broad $\text{O}-\text{H}$ bands.

Electronic spectra and magnetic measurements: Due to the insolubility of the complexes in common solvents, it was not possible to study their solution spectra. Therefore, mull spectra in 200-2000 nm region has been studied. The metal derivatives of ABDP also absorbed in the same regions as those of AEDP. Therefore, only the spectra of AEDP complexes has been discussed in detail.

Manganese(II) complexes: Manganese(II) formed a light pink complex, $\text{Mn}_2(\text{AEDP}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) IN INFRARED SPECTRA OF AEDP AND ITS METAL DERIVATIVES

AEDP	Mn ₂ L.2H ₂ O	Co ₂ L.3H ₂ O	Ni ₂ L.4H ₂ O	Cu ₂ L.2H ₂ O	Zn ₂ L.3H ₂ O	Cd ₂ L.2H ₂ O	Pb ₂ L.H ₂ O	Assignment
3400	3320	3340	3440	3800 br	3360	3400 br	3460	
3160	3210	3260	3340		3280		3400	ν + OH
2960		3120	3200		3200			ν _{NH₂} , ν _{NH₂}
		1650	1620	1625	1620	1620	1620	δ _{O-H} , δ _{N-H}
1680	1625	1620	1560	1155	1140	1120		ν _{P=O}
1200	1110	1120	1120	1110		1110		ν _{asPO₂}
1180	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	ν _{asPO₂}
	1080	1050	1070	1090	1080	1050	1080	ν _{asPO₂}
	1050	1030	1050	1070	1050	1020	1040	ν _{asPO₂}
	1020	1015	1020	1030				
1020	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	ν _{SPO₂}
1000	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	ν _{asP-(OH)₂}
	990	990	950	1000	1000	980	980	ν _{SPO₂}
	910	910	900	920	940	910	—	ν _{SP-(OH)₂}
940	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	

br = Broad.

 TABLE 3—PRINCIPAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) IN INFRARED SPECTRA OF ABDP AND ITS METAL DERIVATIVES

ABDP	Mn ₂ L.H ₂ O	Co ₂ L.2H ₂ O	Ni ₂ L.3H ₂ O	Cu ₂ L.H ₂ O	Zn ₂ L.H ₂ O	Cd ₂ L.H ₂ O	Pb ₂ L.H ₂ O	Assignments
3400 br	3000 br	3260 br	3300 br	3200 br	3340	3360 br	3400	ν _{OH} , ν _{NH₂}
1640	1640	1630	1650	1650		1640		δ _{O-H} , δ _{N-H}
	1630		1640	1630	1680		1620	
1380	1190	1150	1140	1190	1130	1105	1180	ν _{P=O}
	1050	1030	1160	1050	1040	1050	1040	ν _{asPO₂}
	1080							
1010	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	ν _{asP-(OH)₂}
—	980	900	980	990	1000	990	960	ν _{SPO₂}
980	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	ν _{SP-(OH)₂}

br = Broad.

AEDP. It absorbed at 25970, 8330 and 6900 cm⁻¹ in the electronic spectrum. But it is not possible to assign any geometry to the complex on this basis, since diffused transmittance spectra does not give any information about the oscillator strength. Mn₂(ABDP).H₂O is a white solid and hence did not absorb in this region.

The magnetic moment values of 4.12 B.M. for AEDP complex and 4.04 B.M. for ABDP complex are somewhat lower than the expected value, 5.65-6.10 B.M., for d⁵ system⁶. This shows that the system is magnetically concentrated. The metal ions are situated close enough so that there is considerable interaction between them.

Cobalt(II) complexes : The two blue-violet complexes showed electronic spectrum typical of six-coordinate complexes. The absorption bands have been observed at 8160, 16390, 17540 and 20000 cm⁻¹ for Co₂(AEDP).3H₂O and at 8260 (weak), 18020 and 19800 cm⁻¹ for Co₂(ABDP).2H₂O, and the assignments made for these bands are to the excited state terms ⁴T_{2g}(F), ⁴A_{2g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g}(P), respectively from the ground term ⁴T_{1g}(F). The

frequency on visible band at 16390 cm⁻¹ can arise through low symmetry components to the ligand field or through the presence of spin-forbidden transition made evident by intensity stealing from the allowed band¹⁰. The presence of low symmetry components to the ligand field is revealed by the splitting¹¹ of near infrared band 7170, and 8160 cm⁻¹.

The magnetic moment values have been found to be 3.43 and 3.85 B.M. corresponding to Co₂(AEDP).3H₂O and Co₂(ABDP).2H₂O, which indicate that antiferromagnetic interactions are operative.

Nickel(II) complexes : Both the nickel(II) complexes are light green in colour which may be due to the presence of bands in the red and blue portions of the visible spectrum. The three bands at 8440, 14290 and 25000 cm⁻¹ for Ni₂(AEDP).H₂O, and 8300, 13890 and 25640 cm⁻¹ for Ni₂(ABDP).2H₂O are associated with spin-allowed transitions from the ³A_{2g}(F) ground term to the three excited triplet terms ³T_{2g}(F), ³T_{1g}(F), and ³T_{1g}(P), respectively. In case of Ni₂(ABDP).2H₂O complex there are also

Fig. 1. Derivatogram of $\text{Ni}_3(\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{NO}_6\text{P}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (100 mg specimen).

weak bands at ($f \sim 10^{-6}$) in the region of $15000\text{--}18000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (at 15630 and 17390 cm^{-1}) may be attributed to spin-forbidden transitions¹². The three spin-allowed transitions suggest the formation of an octahedral six-coordinate nickel(II) complex. The spin-forbidden transition could be interpreted in terms of spin-orbit coupling.

The magnetic moment for Ni^{II} octahedral in dilute systems are normally found to vary from 2.80 to 3.50 B.M. However, in the $\text{Ni}_3(\text{AEDP})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ni}_3(\text{ABDP})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complexes, magnetic moments have been observed to be 2.31 and 2.50 B.M., respectively. Therefore, like other metal derivatives, these complexes have also been inferred to be magnetically concentrated.

Copper(II) complexes: $\text{Cu}_2(\text{AEDP})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ gave a single broad band in the visible region at 13160 cm^{-1} and has been attributed to ${}^3\text{T}_{2g} \leftarrow {}^3\text{E}_g$ transition in six-coordinated geometry.

The magnetic moment values of 1.45 and 1.32 B.M. for AEDP and ABDP complexes, respectively are lower than the expected value of 1.7–2.20 B.M. range for d^9 system.

Thermal analyses:

Nickel(II)aminobenzylidenediphosphonate: The endothermic effects at 100 and 125' on the D.T.A. curve for $\text{Ni}_3(\text{ABDP})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fig. 1) correspond to the consecutive loss of first and second water molecules, respectively. Two exothermic effects at 370

and 800° are observed. On D.T.A. curve, the corresponding mass loss on T.G. is 26 and 29%, respectively. However, no definite stages of decomposition could be identified after the total loss of water molecules from the complex compound suggesting that the organic part starts decomposing after the total loss of water molecules. The final product is $2\text{NiO.P}_2\text{O}_5$ as inferred from total experimental mass loss of 29.9% (theoretical 30%) of the complex. The formation of the final product of this type has also been reported by Khramov *et al.*⁸ for their rare earth organophosphonic acid complexes.

In case of $\text{Co}_2(\text{AEDP}).3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ the endothermic effect at 140° on D.T.A. curve corresponds to the loss of three molecules of water. The total experimental mass loss of 23% at the formation of $2\text{NiO.P}_2\text{O}_5$ is corroborated by the expected loss of 21.73%.

The properties of these complexes like insolubility in different solvents, their infusibility up to 280°, coordination of phosphoryl oxygen of the ligands to the metal atom and other physico-chemical studies suggest that these may be polymeric in nature.

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